
Certificates as Proof of Land Ownership Rights from an Islamic Legal Perspective

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Abstract:

This study presents three research questions: First, what is the concept of proof of land ownership rights from the perspective of Islamic law? Second, what is the process of issuing land certificates as proof of land ownership rights according to Islamic law? Third, what is the legal force of land certificates as proof of land ownership rights according to Islamic law? The type of research used is library research with a normative theological (sharia) approach. The data sources used are data obtained indirectly (secondary data), including primary sources such as the Qur'an, Hadith, and legislation; secondary sources like literature and scientific journals; and tertiary sources such as magazines, dictionaries, and Google. The results of this study show that: First, the concept of proof of land ownership in Islamic law aims to provide legal certainty regarding land ownership rights. Proof of land ownership can be in the form of written documents (kitabah), testimony (syahadah), and continuous physical control (qabdh wa istighlal). Second, applying Islamic legal principles such as justice (al-'adalah), benefit (al-maslahah), transparency (al-ṣidq), and public announcement (I'lan) in land certificates ensures that the land registration process is conducted fairly, accurately, and openly. Third, land certificates serve as a perfect means of proof in the legal system, providing legal protection for landowners and preventing ownership disputes.

Keywords: Certificate Land, Islamic Law, Property Rights

INTRODUCTION

Etymologically, the word "certificate" comes from the Dutch word "*Certificat*," which means a letter of proof or a letter of reference. So, when we say land certificate, it means a statement proving a person's right to a piece of land. In other words, a land certificate shows that someone owns a particular piece of land and that ownership is supported by substantial evidence in the form of a letter issued by the competent authority. (Chomzah, 2002)

The process of land registration that provides legal certainty is known as *Rechts Cadaster* or *Legal Cadaster*. This process includes certainty of the status of registered rights, the subject of rights, and the object of rights. (Santoso, 2019) Boedi Harsono explains that land registration is a series of actions carried out continuously by the State or government. These actions involve collecting specific information or data in certain areas, processing, storing, and presenting it to benefit the community by providing legal certainty in the field of land, including the creation and maintenance

of evidence. (Harsono, 2011) Through this land registration, land certificates are issued as proof of land rights ownership.

The final result of the land registration process is a certificate indicating the rights to the land. The certificate provides legal assurance regarding who owns the land, its exact location, boundaries, area, and legal rights. This legal assurance offers legal protection to the person whose name is registered on the certificate from third-party interference. (Sutedi, 2006) Land certificates have various vital functions that other objects cannot replace. The primary function, as stipulated in Article 19 paragraph (2) letter c of the Basic Agrarian Law (UUPA), is as strong evidence of land rights. (Sutedi, 2011) In addition, land certificates also give banks or lenders confidence to provide loans to landowners. So, if the landowner is an entrepreneur, this will undoubtedly make it easier for them to obtain loans. Finally, for the government, the existence of land certificates indicates that the land has been registered with the Agrarian Office. Complete information about the land is stored at the land office and can be easily found if needed. This information is crucial for planning development activities, such as urban development, the installation of irrigation pipes and telephone cables, and the imposition of land and building taxes, among others.

Land ownership in Islam is essentially the property of Allah SWT. Humans only manage and utilize what has been provided by Allah SWT.

Ownership of land according to Islamic law can be obtained in several ways, namely through sale and purchase, inheritance, grants, reviving dead land (*ihya' al-mawat*), setting boundaries on dead land (*tahjir*), and free distribution by the State to the people (*iqha*). (Haroen, 2000) The concept of community ownership of land, as outlined by Indonesian Land Law and Islamic Law, shares similarities in legal principles, particularly in fair and equitable land ownership based on equality before the law and religious, spiritual, and ethical values. In Islamic law, land law is known as *Ahkam al-Aradhi*, which covers the rights of ownership (*milkiyah*), management (*tasharruf*), and distribution (*tauzi'*) of land.

The objectives of this study are: *First*, to analyze the concept of proof of land ownership rights from the perspective of Islamic law. *Second*, to explore the process of issuing land certificates as proof of land ownership rights according to Islamic law. *Third*, to analyze the legal force of land certificates as evidence of land ownership rights according to Islamic law.

RESEARCH METHOD

This qualitative research employs a library research approach to explore, understand, and analyze normative concepts related to land certificates as proof of ownership from the perspective of Islamic law. The research design is descriptive-analytical, in which the researcher examines various literature sources to gain a deep understanding of the object of study. The approach used is theological-normative (*sharia*), based on Islamic legal norms and principles as found in the Qur'an, Hadith, and the opinions of scholars and *fiqh* literature. Because this research is based on a literature study, no population and sample are used as in field research.

Data collection techniques were carried out by identifying, reviewing, and examining relevant literature sources, such as Islamic law books, academic textbooks, scientific journals, Indonesian laws and regulations (such as the Basic Agrarian Law and Government Regulation No. 24 of 1997),

and other sources of positive law. The main instrument in this study was the researcher, who was responsible for searching for, selecting, and analyzing data based on the study's focus and objectives.

The collected data were then analyzed using three methods: deductive, to draw specific conclusions from general principles of Islamic law; inductive, to formulate general conclusions from particular data obtained from the literature; and comparative, to compare the principles of Islamic law and Indonesian positive law in terms of proving land ownership through certificates. The results of this analysis are presented systematically to answer the research questions and develop valid conclusions based on verified library data.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. The Concept of Proof of Land Ownership in the Perspective of Islamic Law

Islam teaches that everything in the heavens and on earth, including land, belongs entirely to Allah SWT. As the valid owner, Allah SWT gives authority (*istikhlaf*) to humans to manage and utilize it in accordance with His laws. Actual ownership (*aslul milki*) remains in the hands of Allah SWT, while humans are only given the right to use (*tasarruf*) the land in a manner that is pleasing to Him. During the time of the prophets, land ownership was initially under the authority of the government before being distributed to individuals. The government had the right to grant, restrict, or take back land ownership for the benefit of the community. (Megawati et al., 2022)

Islam establishes various methods to prove land ownership to protect individual rights and prevent disputes. Proof of land ownership in Islam is not only administrative in nature, but also considers moral, social, and Sharia law aspects. Land ownership must be obtained lawfully and must not harm other parties. Historically, during the time of the Prophet Muhammad and the Khulafaur Rasyidin, land ownership was generally recognized through physical control, community testimony, and direct grants from the State. As the system of government and administration developed, record-keeping became an essential instrument in protecting land ownership rights. Therefore, Islam recognizes various forms of proof of ownership, including:

1. Records and Written Documents (*Kitabah*), written documents are documents that have the power to serve as evidence in court proceedings, both to establish and to refute a right. During the time of the Prophet Muhammad (pbuh), the practice of recording land ownership already existed. However, it was not yet in the form of official documents such as today's certificates. For example, when the Prophet Muhammad (peace be upon him) distributed land to Abu Tsalabah al-Khusyani (may Allah be pleased with him), he gave him the land along with a letter of allocation as proof of ownership. (Hariyono, 2021)
2. Testimony (*Syahadah*), in the context of syarah, testimony is defined as a convincing statement, namely information conveyed based on direct experience or through knowledge from others that has been widely disseminated. (Bahansyi, 1984) Testimony from a fair individual is a form of evidence for land ownership recognized in Islam. This testimony plays a crucial role, especially in communities that have not yet implemented a formal land registration system. When someone claims ownership of land, statements from those familiar with the land's history can serve as valid evidence. In some areas that still practice

customary systems, land ownership often depends on the recognition of the local community. In Islam, such testimony retains its legal force as long as honest and trustworthy witnesses deliver it.

3. Sustainable Land Ownership and Utilization (*Qabdh wa Istighlal*), Islam emphasizes that land must be utilized and not left idle. If a person continuously cultivates land without any other party claiming it, then their ownership can be recognized. In some classical Islamic legal systems, if a person owns land but does not manage it for three consecutive years, their ownership rights can be revoked by the State and given to another party who is capable of managing it. This principle aims to ensure that land remains productive and does not become neglected.

B. The Process of Issuing Land Certificates as Proof of Land Ownership Rights According to Islamic Law

The process of issuing land certificates in Indonesia is an administrative and technical procedure carried out through the National Land Agency (BPN). The first stage begins with the preparation and collection of documents by the applicant, which include photocopies of their ID card and family card, proof of land ownership such as a deed of sale or inheritance, a land certificate from the sub-district or village, the latest SPPT PBB (Land and Building Tax) form, a statement of no dispute, and a picture or sketch of the land, if available. Once the documents are complete, the applicant submits an application to the local BPN office by filling out a form and paying the administrative fee, which is determined based on the size and value of the land. Next, BPN officials will conduct a direct measurement of the land at the location to decide on its factual boundaries, and the results will be used to create a map. After that, the land ownership or legal data will be publicly announced in the sub-district or village for 14 days, allowing third parties to file objections if there are disputes or claims over the land. If no objections are received during the announcement period, the BPN will proceed to the final verification and approval of technical and legal data.

According to Islamic law, the process of issuing land certificates applies Islamic legal principles that can be examined based on several main principles, namely:

1. The Principle of Justice (*al-'adalah*). The application of the principle of justice in the realm of land certificates requires that every document issued accurately reflect the data and provide equal protection for all owners. This is achieved through an open and accurate registration process, where information about the owner's identity, land boundaries, and ownership history has been thoroughly verified by competent authorities. This verification process is crucial to prevent potential future disputes and ensure that the recording of land rights is conducted in good faith without any data manipulation. Justice is upheld through transparent access to information for all interested parties.
2. The principle of public interest (*al-maslahah*) is one of the primary considerations in establishing laws, including in the aspect of land. In Islamic law, public interest serves as the primary foundation to ensure that every rule imposed provides tangible benefits to the community and protects them from injustice or harm. In relation to land ownership, the application of this principle aims to provide legal certainty, guarantee legitimate ownership

rights, and avoid conflicts or disputes that can negatively impact individuals and society at large.

3. The principle of transparency (*al-ṣidq*) in Islamic law emphasizes the importance of honesty and openness in various aspects of life, including land ownership and administration. In the context of land certificates, transparency is a fundamental factor in ensuring the validity of ownership rights and preventing potential disputes that could harm individuals and society at large. As legal proof of land ownership, certificates must reflect accurate, transparent, and accountable information. Thus, the principle of transparency ensures that every aspect of land ownership is based on honesty and openness, without manipulation or concealment of facts.
4. The principle of Announcement/Publication (*I'lan*), in the process of issuing land certificates according to Islamic law, is a crucial stage regulated in Indonesia's land registration regulations. This process aims to provide legal certainty and protection to land rights holders and to ensure that no other party objects to or claims rights to the land.

C. Legal Force of Land Certificates as Proof of Land Ownership Rights According to Islamic Law

Certificates as proof of land ownership play a vital role in providing protection and legal certainty for land rights holders. As valid proof of the land registration process, certificates include copies of land registers and letters with legal and physical data about a plot of land, thus serving as strong evidence. Two main aspects underlie the role of certificates, namely:

1. As proof of ownership, in its position as proof of rights, a land certificate indicates the party that is legally entitled to a plot of land.
2. As a strong means of proof, if there is a dispute or legal claim in court regarding certified land, the information contained in the certificate has strong legal force, unless there is other evidence to refute it. (Bur, 2017)

Land certificates from the perspective of Islamic law serve as proof of legal ownership and form the basis for legal protection. Their existence aligns with Islamic principles that emphasize protecting property rights, preventing conflict, and enforcing justice in land ownership and management. From the perspective of maqashid syariah, clear and registered land ownership helps avoid disputes and protect property from unlawful control. This is in line with the principle of hifdz al-maal (protection of property), which affirms that every individual has the right to protection of their property. (Herlindah et al., 2022)

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings, it can be concluded that the concept of proof of land ownership in Islamic law aims to provide legal certainty regarding land ownership rights. Proof of land ownership in Islam can be in the form of written documents (*kitabah*), testimony (*syahadah*), and continuous physical control (*qabdh wa istighlal*). Islamic legal principles such as justice (*al-'adalah*), benefit (*al-maslahah*), transparency (*al-ṣidq*), and public announcement (*I'lan*) are applied in the process of registering and issuing land certificates. The principle of justice emphasizes the importance of data accuracy and equal protection for all landowners. The principle of public interest ensures that land

certificates benefit both owners and the community. The principle of transparency guarantees openness and honesty in the land administration process. The principle of public announcement provides information to the community, ensures openness, and protects the rights of others if there are valid objections or claims.

Land certificates serve as a perfect means of proof in the legal system, both in the context of positive law and Islamic law. Land certificates provide legal certainty and protection for landowners, preventing disputes and ensuring that land can be used productively. From an Islamic perspective, land certificates are also in line with the principle of *hifz al-mal* (preservation of property), which emphasizes the importance of protecting property rights. These findings contribute to the development of science, particularly in the fields of Islamic law and land law. The findings of this study can be used as a reference for academics, researchers, and legal practitioners in understanding the concept of land ownership from an Islamic legal perspective and the application of Sharia principles in the land certification system. For the government, this study emphasizes the importance of improving transparency and accuracy in the land registration process. The government needs to ensure that land certificates are issued based on the principles of justice and benefit, and utilize technology to improve efficiency and accuracy in land administration. For the community, this research provides an understanding of the importance of having a land certificate as proof of legal ownership. The community is expected to be more active in registering their land and understanding their rights and obligations as landowners.

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Certificates as Proof of Land Ownership Rights from an Islamic Legal Perspective

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